

A Priority-Driven, Consistency-Preserving Strategy for the Relocation Problem of Replicated Files*

Uwe M. Borghoff[†]

Institut für Informatik, Technische Universität München
Postfach 20 24 20, D-8000 München 2, Germany

Abstract

Suppose you got an excellent dynamic file assignment algorithm. But, how to proceed dynamically from the current to the optimal file allocation? Imagine replication of your files and some sort of voting strategy — the question then is, how to maintain consistency if the current and the optimal file assignment differ not only in the location of the files but also in the number of replicas?

This paper tries to answer these questions and introduces the basic relocation protocols which preserve consistency during relocation, as well as a priority-driven, storage capacity-based approach to bring the basic relocation protocols in an optimal sequence in order to move quickly and as close as possible towards the optimal file assignment.

1 Introduction

We consider a mathematical model of an information network of $|R|$ nodes, some of which contain copies of our $|D|$ data files. The degree of replicas has not to be fixed.

Within this network, every node is able to communicate with every other node via the network. At a time t , the communication rate between node r_i and node r_j is $rate_t(r_i, r_j)$ [$\frac{blocks}{sec}$]. It holds $\forall t : rate_t(r_i, r_j) = rate_t(r_j, r_i)$; $rate_t(r_i, r_i) = \infty, \forall r_i \in R$.

Most of the nodes are equipped with a disk. At a time t , the free disk space at node r is $fdsp_t(r)$ [$blocks$]. For diskless nodes it holds $\forall t : fdsp_t(r_{diskless}) = 0$.

The information about the location of the files is stored in a so-called *file allocation matrix* AC . The entries at a time t are as follows:

$$AC_t(d, r) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{iff } d \text{ is stored at } r \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{iff } d \text{ is expected to be stored at } r \\ 0, & \text{iff } d \text{ is not stored at } r \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

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[†]e-mail: borghoff@informatik.tu-muenchen.de

Let $RD_t(d)$ be the node set for which holds: $r \in RD_t(d) \iff AC_t(d, r) = 1$.

At a time t , each file $d \in D$ consists of a set $K_t(d)$ of data blocks. Every data block $k \in K_t(d)$ is individually accessed. Due to our replication, we assume a majority consensus voting approach ([13]). Before accessing a data block k of a file d , a quorum must be collected. All nodes r for which $AC_t(d, r) \neq 0$ are asked to vote in case of a read or write request. The quorum size $qu_t(d)$ that must be reached at a time t , is¹

$$qu_t(d) := trunc\left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r)}{2}\right) + 1 \quad (2)$$

Our main goal is the consistency of all the data files D . What do we mean by consistency?

Definition 1.1 $RD_t^{new}(d, k)$ is the set of nodes storing file d at a time t , where the k -th data block of file d has the newest version. \square

Definition 1.2 The data files D are said to be consistent at a time t , iff

$$\forall d \in D \forall k \in K_t(d) : |RD_t^{new}(d, k)| \geq qu_t(d) \quad (3)$$

We try to fulfill two claims:

Claim 1: If a data file d is inconsistent at a time t , no quorum can be reached at this time. Or by other words, only a consistent file d enables successful quorums.

Claim 2: If a data file d is inconsistent, it will eventually become consistent. The period of consistency is short.

Imagine a global file assignment procedure dWAP which dynamically calculates better or even optimal file allocations. Let AC_t^* be the optimal file allocation at a time t .

Many previous papers mention heuristics for this so-called *file assignment problem FAP* ([1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14]). Minimum response time and maximum system throughput are the most common performance objectives ([5]).

In this work, we do not think about the dWAP-optimization and the constraints that must be fulfilled. It is far beyond the scope of this paper to discuss or develop such a dWAP. For us, its existence is a fact.

Our problem is first, how to proceed periodically from a current AC_t to the optimal AC_t^* , and second, how to maintain consistency during the relocation of the files. Since we do not suppose that the number of replicas is fixed, we must deal with different quorum sizes during relocation. Finally, we must proof that our claims are reached.

Organization of the paper

The next section introduces the basic protocols by which the relocation is done. Each basic protocol is shown to preserve consistency. The basic protocols include migration of a file, increase as well as decrease of the number of replicas.

Since there are many possible transitions from AC_t to AC_t^* , section 3 introduces our priority-driven, storage capacity-based approach of relocation.

Finally, section 4 gives a brief outlook to our current research and concludes with a few examples.

¹The function $trunc(x)$ results in the greatest integer n for which holds: $n \leq x$.

2 Basic Relocation Protocols

From time to time, there is a need to relocate some files in order to get the optimal file allocation which is permanently changed by our dWAP procedure. For example, dWAP calculates the best file allocation for the current network traffic in order to minimize the global response time in the network.

This dynamical calculation is not further mentioned. For this paper, it is only interesting that there will always be a difference between the current file allocation and the optimal one. A centralized *relocation procedure* *rWAP* is developed. To proceed from a current file allocation AC_t to a newly calculated optimal file allocation AC_t^* , rWAP uses three basic schemes:

- **migration:**
migrate a file from one node to another.
- **increase the number of replicas:**
create a copy of an existing file at one or more nodes.
- **decrease the number of replicas:**
delete a copy of a given file at one or more nodes.

For each of these schemes a basic protocol is given that achieves consistency during all steps of the protocols.

2.1 Migration Protocol

Let us assume a migration of a given file d from node r_i to node r_j , $i \neq j$. The migration starts at a time t . It holds:

$$AC_t(d, r_i) = 1 \text{ and } AC_t(d, r_j) = 0$$

Step 1: rWAP changes file allocation to

$$AC_t(d, r_i) = \frac{1}{2} \text{ and } AC_t(d, r_j) = \frac{1}{2}$$

This modification is atomic. This implies that the read or write quorum sizes are not changed. On the other hand, since r_i as well as r_j have AC -entries $\neq 0$, both nodes are asked to vote. It should be clear that only one node is allowed to vote positively.

Step 2: rWAP asks r_i for a not yet transmitted data block of file d .

Step 3: r_i looks for a not yet transmitted data block of file d . If there is one, r_i checks whether it is transmissible. A data block is said to be **transmissible**, iff there are no outstanding locks for any read or write request. If there exists such a transmissible block, r_i transmits this block. For any incoming voting request for this particular block, now r_i gives a negative vote. Hence, r_i will no longer participate in a quorum corresponding to this data block.

Step 4: rWAP sends the transmitted block to node r_j and asks to store it.

Step 5: r_j accepts the data block. From now on, r_j is able to give a positive vote for any incoming read or write request.

Step 6: Go back to step 2, as long as there are any data blocks missing.

Step 7: The entire file d is transmitted to r_j . rWAP gives the command to erase the d -copy from node r_i and changes file allocation to

$$AC_t(d, r_i) = 0 \text{ und } AC_t(d, r_j) = 1$$

Theorem 2.1 *Migration of files does not endanger consistency.*

Proof: Migration does not endanger consistency because the number of replicas is the same before and after migration. During migration, there is a slight chance that a quorum for a particular data block is not reached. For a moment or two, both r_i and r_j reject any request. But eventually, exactly one node will reply positively. At no time during migration, both nodes reply positively for a voting request to the same data block. \square

2.2 Increase Protocol

To increase the number of replicas, new file copies will be created at nodes which do not possess a copy. Every newly created file copy consists of the newest data blocks. Let new copies of file d be created at the node set $INS_t(d)$. The increase starts at a time t . It holds: $INS_t(d) \cap RD_t(d) = \emptyset$, $0 < |INS_t(d)| < |R| - |RD_t(d)|$.

Step 1: rWAP calculates the current quorum size *insquorum* for requests to file d .

$$insquorum := qu_t(d)$$

Step 2: rWAP changes file allocation to

$$\forall r \in INS_t(d): AC_t(d, r) = 1$$

Hence, the entries in the file allocation matrix are installed as they should be **after** the increase. From now on, every reader or writer is obliged to get a greater quorum size.

Step 3: Block by block, rWAP asks for the newest data of file d . Therefore, it uses the normal read operation, but still the old quorum size *insquorum*.

Step 4: Block by block, rWAP transmits the entire file d to all nodes r in $INS_t(d)$ (see Step 4 of the migration protocol).

Step 5: Each r accepts every block and votes positively for any read or write request concerning the accepted data blocks.

Theorem 2.2 *Increase of replicas does not endanger consistency.*

Proof: (by induction)

At a time t , the file system is consistent (cf. (3)). There is an increase of n , $0 < n \leq |R| - |RD_t(d)|$, new copies of file d . These copies are freshly created at the node set $INS_t(d)$. It holds: $|INS_t(d)| = n$. The increase is completed at a time t' . Hence, at a time t' , $t \prec t'$:

$$\sum_{r \in R} AC_{t'}(d, r) = \sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) + n \quad (4)$$

$$\forall k \in K_{t'}(d) : |RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k)| = |RD_t^{new}(d, k)| + n \quad (5)$$

$$\forall r \in INS_t(d) \forall k \in K_{t'}(d) : r \in RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k) \quad (6)$$

At a time t' , the file system is consistent again, because $\forall d \in D \forall k \in K_{t'}(d)$:

$$|RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k)| \geq qu_t(d) + n \quad (7)$$

$$= \text{trunc} \left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R} AC_{t'}(d, r) - n}{2} \right) + 1 + n \quad (8)$$

$$\geq qu_{t'}(d) + n - \text{trunc} \left(\frac{n}{2} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\geq qu_{t'}(d) \quad (10)$$

(7) holds through (3) and (5). (8) holds through (4). (9) holds through definition of *trunc* and (10), because $n > 0$. \square

2.3 Decrease Protocol

Decrease of the number of replicas is done by the deletion of existing copies in a set of nodes. Let copies of file d be deleted at the node set $DEL_t(d)$. The decrease starts at a time t . It holds: $DEL_t(d) \subset RD_t(d)$, $0 < |DEL_t(d)| < |RD_t(d)|$.

Step 1: rWAP asks all nodes r in $DEL_t(d)$ to delete file d . Before that, rWAP transmits a value

$$\text{delquorum} := \text{trunc} \left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R \setminus DEL_t(d)} AC_t(d, r)}{2} \right) + 1$$

to all $r \in DEL_t(d)$. This value *delquorum* equals the quorum size which is actually necessary **after** the decrease.

Step 2: Every node $r \in DEL_t(d)$ which gets the deletion task, automatically votes negatively to any read or write request for file d .

Step 3: Before the deletion of file d , each r performs as follows:

- r looks for a data block of file d which is not locked by a read or write request (i. e. transmissible).
- Such a data block together with its version number is transmitted along with a normal write operation to at least *delquorum* nodes.

Each transmission is successful if either the block is updated or rejected because of its old version number. This strategy is necessary because it is the only way to guarantee that there are no deletions of newest blocks, without updating the rest of the world.

Step 4: Repeat step 3 until all data blocks are tried to be remotely updated.

Step 5: rWAP changes file allocation for every r which acknowledges the deletion of file d , by $AC_t(d, r) = 0$.

Definition 2.1 $RD_t^{old \rightarrow new}(d, k)$ is the set of nodes which have exchanged their data block k copy of file d during step 3 of the decrease protocol. \square

Theorem 2.3 *Decrease of replicas does not endanger consistency.*

Proof: (by induction)

At a time t , the file system is consistent. There is a decrease of n , $0 < n < |RD_t(d)|$, copies of the file d at the node set $DEL_t(d)$.

It holds: $|DEL_t(d)| = n$. Decrease is completed at a time t' . Hence, at a time t' , $t \prec t'$:

$$\sum_{r \in R} AC_{t'}(d, r) = \sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) - n \quad (11)$$

$$\forall k \in K_{t'}(d) : |RD_t^{old \rightarrow new}(d, k)| \geq qu_{t'}(d) - |RD_t^{new}(d, k) \setminus DEL_t(d)| \quad (12)$$

$$\forall k \in K_{t'}(d) : |RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k)| = |RD_t^{new}(d, k) \setminus DEL_t(d)| + |RD_t^{old \rightarrow new}(d, k)| \quad (13)$$

At a time t' , the file system is consistent again, because

$$\forall d \in D \forall k \in K_{t'}(d) : |RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k)| \geq qu_{t'}(d) \quad (14)$$

(14) holds through (12) and (13). \square

Theorem 2.4 *Relocation of files does not endanger the consistency of the file system.*

Proof: Every possible relocation can be trivially separated and sequenced into the basic protocols shown above. It has been shown that each basic protocol itself does not endanger consistency, so there is no harm for the whole relocation. \square

The basic protocols prevent access to inconsistent data. Our block-oriented scheme shortens the period of inconsistency. All files will eventually become consistent. Therefore, both claims are reached.

The next thing to show, is how to separate a relocation into a well-defined, optimal sequence of the basic protocols.

3 Relocation Strategy

The free disk space at the nodes limits the range of possible transitions from AC_t to AC_t^* . Since the relocation process is dynamical, our goal is to proceed very quickly and as close as possible towards AC_t^* .

For each file d , the possible differences between AC_t and AC_t^* consist of

- location of replicas changed or/and
- number of replicas decreased or
- number of replicas increased

We develop five different variants. Each variant gets a different priority. At a time t , exactly one variant comes true. Automatically, this variant possesses the highest priority and will be executed.

Files are ordered by their sizes $|K_t(d)|$. If there are executable variants for a set of files with the same priority, the variant for the smallest file is executed.

Let d be the considered file. The possible variants are as follows:

1. Pure decrease of d -replicas.

This variant holds, iff

- $\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) > \sum_{r \in R} AC_t^*(d, r)$ and
- $\forall r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 0 \implies AC_t^*(d, r) = 0$ and
- $\forall r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 1 \implies AC_t^*(d, r) = 0 \vee AC_t^*(d, r) = 1$

This variant gets the highest priority, because storage space is released and no migrations need to be executed. The following basic relocation protocol will be initiated:

Delete all d -copies at the node set

$$DEL_t(d) := \{r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 1 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r) = 0\}$$

2. Pure migrations of d -copies.

This variant holds, iff

- $\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) = \sum_{r \in R} AC_t^*(d, r)$

This variant gets a lower priority, since the storage space within the network is unchanged. The candidates for migration are selected as follows:

LOOP: Find for every node r_j , for which holds:

$$AC_t(d, r_j) = 0 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r_j) = 1 \wedge fdsp_t(r_j) \geq |K_t(d)|$$

the best corresponding node r_i , for which holds:

$$rate_t(r_i, r_j) = \max_{r \in R: AC_t(d, r) = 1 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r) = 0} rate_t(r, r_j)$$

From all resulting combinations r_j/r_i , choose the one with the best communication rate $rate_t$. Let r_j^*/r_i^* be this combination. The following basic relocation protocol will be initiated: Migrate file d from node r_i^* to node r_j^* . A desirable side effect of this strategy is the deletion of an unwanted d -copy at node r_i .

goto LOOP.

3. Decrease of d -replicas, although new d -copies need to be created at some nodes.

This variant holds, iff

- $\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) > \sum_{r \in R} AC_t^*(d, r)$ and
- $\exists r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 0 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r) = 1$

This variant gets an even lower priority, since storage space is released. But first, a few migrations are necessary. The candidates for migration are selected as in variant 2.

When all migrations are successfully done, one of the other variants will come true.

4. Increase of d -replicas and migration of some d -copies.

This variant holds, iff

- $\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) < \sum_{r \in R} AC_t^*(d, r)$ and
- $\exists r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 1 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r) = 0$

This variant gets an even lower priority, since free storage space is consumed. But first, a few migrations can be done. The candidates for migration are selected as follows:.

LOOP: Find for every node r_i , for which holds:

$$AC_t(d, r_i) = 1 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r_i) = 0$$

the best corresponding node r_j , for which holds:

$$rate_t(r_i, r_j) = \max_{r \in R: AC_t(d, r) = 0 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r) = 1 \wedge fdspt(r) \geq |K_t(d)|} rate_t(r_i, r)$$

From all resulting combinations r_i/r_j , choose the one with the best communication rate $rate_t$.

Let r_i^*/r_j^* be this combination. The following basic relocation protocol will be initiated:

Migrate file d from node r_i^* to node r_j^* .

goto LOOP.

When all executable migrations are successfully done, one of the other variants will come true.

5. Pure increase of d -replicas.

This variant holds, iff

- $\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r) < \sum_{r \in R} AC_t^*(d, r)$ and
- $\forall r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 1 \implies AC_t^*(d, r) = 1$ and
- $\forall r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 0 \implies AC_t^*(d, r) = 0 \vee AC_t^*(d, r) = 1$

This variant gets the lowest priority, since storage space is consumed. The following basic relocation protocol will be initiated:

Create new d -copies at the node set

$$INS_t(d) := \{r \in R : AC_t(d, r) = 0 \wedge AC_t^*(d, r) = 1 \wedge fdspt(r) \geq |K_t(d)|\}$$

4 Conclusion and Examples

Our current research looks for a dWAP-procedure. Since all dWAP-procedures have to deal with NP-hard calculations ([6]), a feasible heuristic will be developed. Furthermore, Thomas' voting algorithm will be modified to be suited to our replication scheme.

Next, we give two examples for the basic increase and decrease protocols. Finally, an example shows how the main relocation strategy works.

Increase Example

We consider file d at a time t . It holds: $K_t(d) = \{k_1, k_2\}$, $RD_t(d) = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$.

node r_1	node r_2	node r_3	node r_4	node r_5
k_{1old}	k_{1new}	k_{1new}	—	—
k_{2new}	k_{2old}	k_{2new}	—	—

This leads to the following quorum size:

$$qu_t(d) := trunc\left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r)}{2}\right) + 1 = 2$$

At time t , d is consistent, because: $RD_t^{new}(d, k_1) = \{r_2, r_3\}$ and $RD_t^{new}(d, k_2) = \{r_1, r_3\}$.

Let $INS_t(d)$ be $\{r_4\}$. At a time t' , the increase is completed and it holds:

node r_1	node r_2	node r_3	node r_4	node r_5
$k_{1_{old}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	—
$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{old}}$	$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{new}}$	—

$RD_{t'}(d) = \{r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4\}$. This leads to the quorum size:

$$qu_{t'}(d) := trunc\left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R} AC_{t'}(d, r)}{2}\right) + 1 = 3$$

At time t' , d is consistent again, because:

$RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k_1) = \{r_2, r_3, r_4\}$ and $RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k_2) = \{r_1, r_3, r_4\}$.

Decrease Example

It holds: $K_t(d) = \{k_1, k_2\}$, $RD_t(d) = \{r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4, r_5\}$

node r_1	node r_2	node r_3	node r_4	node r_5
$k_{1_{old}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{old}}$
$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{old}}$	$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{old}}$

Hence, $qu_t(d) := trunc\left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R} AC_t(d, r)}{2}\right) + 1 = 3$

At time t , d is consistent, because:

$RD_t^{new}(d, k_1) = \{r_2, r_3, r_4\}$ and $RD_t^{new}(d, k_2) = \{r_1, r_3, r_4\}$.

Let $DEL_t(d) = \{c_2\}$. This leads to

$$delquorum = trunc\left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R \setminus DEL_t(d)} AC_t(d, r)}{2}\right) + 1 = 3$$

Let node r_2 transmit his data blocks to the node set $\{r_1, r_3, r_4\}$. Let r_5 be crashed. Three nodes are sufficient (cf. *delquorum*) to maintain consistency.

At a time t' , the decrease is completed and it holds: $RD_{t'}(d) = \{r_1, r_3, r_4, r_5\}$

node r_1	node r_2	node r_3	node r_4	node r_5
$k_{1_{new}}$	—	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{new}}$	$k_{1_{old}}$
$k_{2_{new}}$	—	$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{new}}$	$k_{2_{old}}$

Hence, $qu_{t'}(d) := trunc\left(\frac{\sum_{r \in R} AC_{t'}(d, r)}{2}\right) + 1 = 3$

At time t' , d is consistent again, because:

$RD_{t'}^{old \rightarrow new}(d, k_1) = \{r_1\}$ and therefore, $RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k_1) = \{r_1, r_3, r_4\} = RD_{t'}^{new}(d, k_2)$.

Relocation Example

Now we give a simple example showing our relocation strategy under work. Let us consider a network of 10 nodes. Each node has enough storage capacity to store a copy of file d_j . Let d_j be the considered file for relocation and AC_t resp. AC_t^* the current resp. the optimal file allocation matrices at a time t . AC_t^* is unchanged during our example.

$AC_t^* (j\text{-th row})$									
r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}
1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1

$AC_t (j\text{-th row})$									
r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}
1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	<u>1</u>	1

rWAP checks the variants. It holds:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{10} AC_t(d_j, r_i) = 4 < 6 = \sum_{i=1}^{10} AC_t^*(d_j, r_i)$$

and for node r_9 :

$$AC_t(d_j, r_9) = 1 \wedge AC_t^*(d_j, r_9) = 0$$

Hence, variant 4 comes true. There are possible migrations from r_9 to r_2 or r_5 or r_8 , because

$$AC_t(d_j, r_i) = 0 \wedge AC_t^*(d_j, r_i) = 1, i \in \{2, 5, 8\}$$

Let r_8 be the target of migration. At a time t' , the following allocation matrix is installed:

$AC_{t'} (j\text{-th row})$									
r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}
1	0	1	0	0	0	0	<u>1</u>	0	1

Now, rWAP checks the variants again. It holds:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{10} AC_{t'}(d_j, r_i) = 4 < 6 = \sum_{i=1}^{10} AC_t^*(d_j, r_i)$$

$\forall r_i \in \{r_1, \dots, r_{10}\}$:

$$AC_{t'}(d_j, r_i) = 1 \implies AC_t^*(d_j, r_i) = 1$$

$$AC_{t'}(d_j, r_i) = 0 \implies AC_t^*(d_j, r_i) = 0 \vee AC_t^*(d_j, r_i) = 1$$

Hence, variant 5 comes true.

New d_j -copies will be created at the node set: $INS_{t'}(d_j) := \{r_2, r_5\}$

At a time t'' , the creation of the new file copies is completed. This yields to the following **optimal** file allocation matrix:

$AC_{t''} = AC_t^* (j\text{-th row})$									
r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}
1	<u>1</u>	1	0	<u>1</u>	0	0	1	0	1

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